

The Moderating Role Of Emotional Intelligence Between Academic Procrastination And Academic Achievement Among Male And Female University Students

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>The present research is designed to evaluate the relationship among emotional intelligence, academic procrastination and academic achievement in male and female University students. Further, to explore the moderating role of emotional intelligence between academic procrastination and academic achievement in male and female University students. Purposive sampling technique was employed based on cross-sectional design. Sample consisted 304 University students (male students, n = 94; female students, n = 210). Two scales were employed to assess the academic procrastination and emotional intelligence in university students. The results revealed that Academic Procrastination was negatively correlated and significant with emotional intelligence ($r = -.33, p < .001$). However, non-significantly correlated with previous class GPA ($r = -.05, n.s$) and current class GPA ($r = -.14, n.s$) for male University students. The result also elaborated that Academic Procrastination was negatively correlated and significant with emotional intelligence ($r = -.09, p < .001$), but also non-significant correlated with previous class GPA ($r = .02, n.s$) and current class GPA ($r = -.03, n.s$) for female male University students. Results further revealed that female students were predisposed more emotional intelligence and academic achievement as compare to male students. On the other hand, results explained that male students were more inclined to have academic procrastination as compared to female students. Our analysis results revealed that emotional intelligence acted as a moderator between academic procrastination and previous class GPA in female students. The study acclaimed that those female and male students who experienced academic procrastination, they get low marks in previous class with lower emotional intelligence as compare to those female and male students who exhibited higher emotional intelligence. Recommendations of the latest study are that male and female university students can equally be beneficial but male students can get more benefit by an intervention addressing to academic procrastination. This study would be helpful in educational settings to resolve the emotional problems of students that drag towards reducing academic procrastination and improvement of the academic achievement.</i></p>
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Introduction

Numerous previous studies have consistently reported relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement which also explained inverse relationship (Akinsola, Tella, & Tella, 2007; Balkis & Duru, 2010; Baumeister & Tice, 1997; Fritzsche, Young, & Hickson, 2003; Jackson, Weiss, Lundquist, & Hooper, 2001; Özer, Demir, & Ferrari, 2009; Schouwenburg, 1995; Tice, 1997). Academic performance was predicted by Academic Procrastination in various ways (Jackson et al., 2001). There are four ways in which Procrastination interrupts academic achievement in different pedagogical settings; (i) Procrastinators are unable to complete their school tasks within prearranged time because of their anxious behavior (Schouwenburg, 1995). (ii) Procrastinators are unable to focus on appropriate time and effort which is necessary to perform well because of underestimating the amount of time required for specific tasks (McCown, 1986). (iii) Procrastinators are incapable to perform well because of out of the blue obstacles or delays (Ferrari & Emmons, 1995). (iv) Procrastinators have frequently reported that they work well under pressure situation and time. Various researches reported that "stress was associated with attempting to meet a fast-approach deadline can also impede optimal performance" (Baumeister & Tice, 1997).

Prior research has revealed that academic procrastination is negatively related with academic performance (Akinsola et al., 2007; Balkis & Duru, 2010; Fritzsche et al., 2003; Jackson et al., 2001; Özer et al., 2009). Considering the above researches, academic procrastination is negatively related to academic

achievement. The other important factor that influences student's academic achievement is irrational beliefs (Sapp, 1996).

Academic Procrastination and Emotional Intelligence

Many prior research results are consistently documented that there is a negative relationship between academic procrastination and emotional intelligence (Chow, 2011; Deniz, Tras, & Aydogan, 2009; E. Heward, 2010; E. O. Heward, 2010). People with high emotional intelligence pay greater attention to their own emotions, they have better emotional clarity than others and are capable of emotional healing and thus are able to complete their activities in time (E. O. Heward, 2010).

Gender and Academic Procrastination

Several previous studies were elaborated that gender differences existed on academic procrastination (Else-Quest, Hyde, Goldsmith, & Van Hulle, 2006; Feingold, 1994). Previous investigations on gender differences were explained that there have been found mix and confuse findings on academic procrastination (Feingold, 1994). Male students show academic procrastination as compared to female students. On other hand, contrary studies explained that female students experience more academic procrastinations than male students (Else-Quest et al., 2006).

Emotional intelligence and gender

Many earlier studies have explained that gender differences existed on emotional intelligence (Sutarso, 1999) (Carysi, 2001). Female students were more predisposed to have emotional intelligence as compared male students. It was observed that men are less emotionally expressive than women because they can understand and recognize emotions better. Previous similar study was conducted to explore role of gender between Grade Point Average and Emotional Intelligence. Current study explained that female students who experience emotional intelligence, they show better academic performance as compared to male who don't experience emotional intelligence (Sutarso, 1999).

Academic Achievement and Gender

A large number of prior studies have explained that gender differences existed on academic achievement for last few decades (Eitle, 2005). Female students show high academic achievement as compared male students (Chambers & Schreiber, 2004). Similarly, study has elaborated that demographic variables such as gender, ethnicity, and father's occupation are notorious and crucial factors for student's academic achievement (McCoy, 2005). Prior contrary study has explained that male students are more likely to be superior in academic performance than female students (Abubakar & Bada, 2012).

The latest study was planned to assess the fundamental contribution of previous theoretically suitable but unseen variables to see the impact of academic achievement of Pakistani male and female students. This latest research elaborated future antecedent of academic achievement and also explore consequence of academic procrastination in Pakistani student's career. The relationship of three overlook variables were observed, i.e. academic procrastination, emotional intelligence, and academic achievement which would be predicted by demographic variable such as gender in Pakistani students. The latest research investigated the moderating role of emotional intelligence between procrastination and academic achievement among male and female university students.

Method

Objectives

- 1- To investigate the moderating role of emotional intelligence between academic procrastination and academic achievement among male and female university students.

Hypotheses

- 1- Procrastination is negatively correlated with academic achievement and emotional intelligence among male and female university students.
- 2- There is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement.
- 3- Male students show more academic procrastination than female students.
- 4- Female students show more academic achievement and emotional intelligence as compared to male students.

Research design

The research design was cross-sectional based on quantitative approach. The sample was chosen through purposive sampling technique.

Sample

The site of data collection was different university students of Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Purposive sampling technique was employed through cross-sectional design. Sample was comprised of 304 students (male

students, n = 94; female students, n = 210) with age ranged 18-39. They belong to different socio economic status and different educational level.

Table 1

Frequency and percentages of sample on gender, age, social economic status, educational level (N = 304)

Variables	f.	%
Gender		
Male	210	69%
Female	94	31%
Education		
Bachelors	218	71%
Masters	86	29%
Social economic status		
Low	38	12%
Middle	177	59%
High	89	29%

Operational definition of variables

Procrastination. (Lay, 1986) attributes procrastination to overestimating and underestimating the time it takes to complete a task. Procrastination is characterized as the avoidance of doing a task which needs to be accomplished and to delay the behavior and choosing the more pleasurable activity rejecting to the less pleasure one. Procrastination is to delay the work and waiting for the deadline. And the work is usually done until the last minute of the deadline. Often students miss the deadline and ask for more time. In this research the focus is on student's procrastinating behavior (Olpin & Hesson, 2015).

Emotional Intelligence. It is the ability to monitor one's own and others feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions (Salovey & Mayer, 1990).

Academic Achievement. It is characterized as the evaluation of individual performance on different tasks that involves competition with others according to some standard of excellence. In the present study, academic performance is operationally defined as the student's GPA (Nasiriyani, 2011).

Instruments:

Following instruments were used in current study.

Lay's General Procrastination Scale. It was developed by (Lay, 1986). It was designed to assess academic procrastination in students. It consists of 81 items and Responses are rated on a 5 -point Likert scale from "strongly disagree" = 1 to "strongly agree" = 5. Higher scores are explained more prevalence of academic procrastination. Lower scores are shown less prevalence of academic procrastination. Cronbach alpha of academic procrastination was .82 and a test retest reliability of .80 (Lay, 1986).

Emotional Intelligence Scale. Emotional Intelligence Scale was developed by Wong & Law, (2002), It was employed to assess emotional intelligence. It comprised 16 items. Responses are rated on a 6-point Likert scale from "strongly disagree" = 1 to "strongly agree" = 6. Higher scores on displayed more occurrence of Emotional Intelligence. Lower scores are explained less occurrence of Emotional Intelligence.

Academic Achievement. It is characterized as for measuring academic achievement previous class GPA and first term class GPA were considered in academic achievement of students.

Procedure

In the present study data of 304 students were collected from various public and government Universities of the twin city Islamabad and Rawalpindi. Participant of the current research were approached by permission of University administration. Nature of current study and research objectives were enlightened time of data collection. It assured of Universities authorities and administration that study results would be kept confidential and would only be employed for the research endeavor. Purposive sampling technique was employed through correlation/cross sectional design. Each individual was given the consent form. Then the scales were handed over to the students. There was no fixed time limit for completing the questionnaires.

Results

Table 2

Cronbach alpha of Emotional Intelligence and Procrastination, Correlation matrix between Emotional Intelligence, Procrastination and Academic Achievement University students (N=304).

Variables	M	SD	α	1	2	3	4
1. EQ	68.15	68.15	.88	-			
2. PRO	59.71	59.71	.71	-.171**	-		
3. PCG	76.71	10.64	-	.16**	.016	-	
4. CCG	76.08	10.92	-	.19**	-.049	.776**	-

Note.PCG=Previous Class GPA;CCG= Current Class GPA; EQ =Emotional Intelligence; PRO=Procrastination *P<.05, **P<.01,***P<.000.

Cronbach Alpha Reliability. The table displays that alpha coefficient of the emotional intelligence scale is highly significant which have reliability 0.89. The table further reveals that alpha coefficient of the Academic Procrastination scale is 0.71 highly significant. This is show quite satisfactory reliability.

Correlation among Procrastination, Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement

The table revealed that Academic Procrastination was negatively significant correlated with emotional intelligence ($r = -.17$, $p < .001$), but non-significant correlated with Previous Class GPA ($r = .016$, n.s.) and Current Class GPA ($r = -.05$, n.s) for university students. Regarding to hypothesis 1 " Procrastination is a negative correlated with academic achievement and emotional intelligence among male and female university students." was partially approved.

The table revealed that emotional intelligence was positively significant correlated with Previous Class GPA ($r = .16$, $p < .001$) and Current Class GPA ($r = .19$, $p < .001$).Regarding to hypothesis 2 "There is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement" was approved.

Table 3

Cronbach alpha of Emotional Intelligence and Procrastination, Correlation matrix between Emotional Intelligence, Procrastination and Academic Achievement among male and female students.

Variables	1	2	3	4
1. PRO	-	-.33**	-.05	-.14
2. EQ	-.09	-	.16	.10
3. PCG	.02	.15*	-	.70**
4. CCG	-.03	.23**	.81**	-

Note.Upper diagonal is for Female students ($n = 94$) and lower diagonal is for Male students ($n = 210$). Note.PCG=Previous Class GPA;CCG= Current Class GPA; EQ =Emotional Intelligence; PRO=Procrastination *P<.05, **P<.01,***P<.000.

Correlation among Procrastination, Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement

The table revealed that Academic Procrastination was negatively significant correlated with emotional intelligence ($r = -.33$, $p < .001$). However, non-significant negatively correlated with Previous Class GPA ($r = -.05$, n.s) and Current Class GPA ($r = -.14$, n.s) for male University students.The table further elaborated that Academic Procrastination was negatively significant correlated with emotional intelligence ($r = -.09$, $p < .001$), but also non-significant correlated with Previous Class GPA ($r = .02$, n.s) and Current Class GPA ($r = -.03$, n.s) for female male University students. Regarding to hypothesis 1 "Procrastination is negatively correlated with Academic Achievement and Emotional Intelligence among male and female university students" was partially approved.

The table revealed that emotional intelligence was positively significant correlated with Previous Class GPA ($r = .16$, n.s) and Current Class GPA ($r = .10$, n.s) for male University students.The table further explained that emotional intelligence was positively significant correlated with Previous Class GPA ($r = .15$, $p < .05$) and Current Class GPA ($r = .23$, $p < .001$) for female male University students. Regarding to hypothesis 2 " There is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement " was approved.

Table 4

Variables	Males		Females		$t(df)$	p	95% CI	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
PRO	60	9.7	58	9.3	-2.12(30)	.035	-4.77	-.177

EQ	67	13.32	68.72	13.04	-1.11(30)	.05	-5.02	1.391
PCG	73.98	10.566	77.97	10.5	-3.01(28)	.003	-6.60	-1.389
CCG	73.90	10.863	77.09	10.831	-2.34(29)	.020	-5.86	-.506

Note. PCM=Previous Class Marks; CCM= Current Class Marks; EQ =Emotional Intelligence; PRO=Procrastination *P<.05, **P<.01,***P<.000.

The table results explained mean difference between males and females on procrastination, emotional intelligence and academic achievement. Table further revealed that female students are shown more emotional intelligence and academic achievement as compare to male students. Regarding to hypothesis 4 which states "Female students are shown more academic achievement and emotional intelligence as compared to male students" has been approved.

Table also elaborated that male students are shown more academic procrastination as compared to female students. Regarding to hypothesis 3 "Male students show more academic procrastination than female students".

Table 5

Skewness and Kurtosis for Emotional Intelligence, Academic Achievement for University students (N=304).

Variables	N	Min	Max	M	SD	S	K
PRO	304	31	90	59.71	9.468	-.109	.926
EQ	304	24	94	68.16	13.133	-.561	.107
PCG	304	50	98	76.71	10.643	-.009	-.684
CCG	304	49	98	76.08	10.924	-.035	-.704

Note. PCG=Previous Class GPA; CCG= Current Class GPA; EQ =Emotional Intelligence; PRO=Procrastination *P<.05, **P<.01,***P<.000.

Table reveals that skewness and kurtosis value of emotional intelligence, procrastination and academic achievement are less than to 3. It reflects that data of all study variables are normal distributed.

Table 6

The moderating role of Emotional Intelligence between Procrastination and Academic Achievement among male and female University students.

DV	IV	B	S.E.	B	ΔR^2
Male Students					
PCG	Procrastination	.003	.081	.002	.000
	Emotional intelligence	.117	.057	.147*	
	Procrastination *Emotional intelligence	-.008	.659	-.001	
	Constant	69.828	6.094		
Female Student					
PCG	Procrastination	-.118	.116	-.108	.06
	Emotional intelligence	.100	.088	.127	
	Procrastination *Emotional intelligence	-2.115	.893	-.250**	
	Constant	74.809	7.562		

Note. PCG=Previous Class GPA; CCG= Current Class GPA, *P<.05, **P<.01,***P<.000.

Table elaborated that academic Procrastination was a significant predictor for Previous Class GPA among male and female students. Results of table also revealed that Emotional intelligence was a significant predictor for Previous Class GPA ($B = -.147, p < .05$) in male students. On the other hand, Emotional intelligence was non-significant predictor for Previous Class GPA ($B = -.127, n.s$) in female students. The result indicated that interaction between academic Procrastination and Emotional intelligence was a significant predictor for Previous Class GPA ($B = -.25, p < .001$) in female students. Our study results revealed that emotional intelligence is significant moderator between procrastination and previous class GPA in female students. Regarding to objective 1 which states "To investigate the moderating role of emotional intelligence between academic procrastination, academic achievement among male and female university students." was partially approved.

Figure 1. The moderating role of Emotional Intelligence between Procrastination and Previous Class GPA in Male students.

A significant slope in Figure elaborated that those male students who were experienced academic procrastination, they had get lower marks in previous class with lower emotional intelligence as compare to those male students who had shown higher emotional intelligence.

Figure 2. The moderating role of Emotional Intelligence between Procrastination and Previous Class GPA in female students.

A significant slope in Figure 2 displayed that those female students who were experienced academic procrastination, they get low marks in previous class with lower emotional intelligence as compare to those female students who show higher emotional intelligence.

Discussion

The present research is designed to evaluate the relationship among emotional intelligence, academic procrastination and academic achievement in male and female University students. Further, to explore the moderating role emotional intelligence between academic procrastination and academic achievement in male and female University students.

Regarding to hypothesis 1 which states "Academic Procrastination is negatively correlated with academic achievement and emotional intelligence among male and female university students" was partially approved in present research. Results show in table 3 revealed that Academic Procrastination was negatively significant correlated with emotional intelligence ($r = -.33, p < .001$). However, non-significant negatively correlated with Previous Class *GPA* ($r = -.05, n.s$) and Current Class *GPA* ($r = -.14, n.s$) for male University students. The table further elaborated that Academic Procrastination was negatively non-significant correlated with emotional intelligence ($r = -.09, p < .001$), Previous Class *GPA* ($r = .02, n.s$) and Current Class *GPA* ($r = -.03, n.s$) for female male University students. Numerous Previous studies findings were supported current study results that academic procrastination was negatively correlated with academic achievement (Akinsola et al., 2007; Balkis & Duru, 2010; Baumeister & Tice, 1997; Fritzsche et al., 2003; Jackson et al., 2001; Özer et al., 2009; Schouwenburg, 1995). Several prior research results were approved present study findings that emotional intelligence was also negatively correlated with academic procrastination (Chow, 2011; E. O. Heward, 2010) Deniz, Tras, & Aydogan, 2009; Heward, 2010).

Regarding to hypothesis 2 which states "There is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement" was partially approved in present research. Results shown in table 3 revealed that emotional intelligence was positively significant correlated with Previous Class *GPA* ($r = .16, n.s$) and Current Class *GPA* ($r = .10, n.s$) for male University students. The table further explained that emotional intelligence was positively significant correlated with Previous Class *GPA* ($r = .15, p < .05$) and Current Class *GPA* ($r = .23, p < .001$) for female male University students. Previous similar study results were approved current research finding that those students who experienced emotional intelligence, they had get better academic performance as compared to those students who had not experience emotional intelligence (Sutarso, 1999).

Regarding to hypothesis 3 " Male students show more academic procrastination than female students " was proved in present research. Results shown in table 4 revealed that male students show more academic procrastination as compared to female students. Several previous studies were elaborated that gender differences existed on academic procrastination (Else-Quest et al., 2006; Feingold, 1994). Various previous studies on gender differences explained that there are mixed and confused findings on academic procrastination (Feingold, 1994). This study finding supported current research results that Male students show academic procrastination as compared to female students. On the other hand, contrary studies explained that female students experienced more academic procrastinations than male students (Else-Quest et al., 2006).

Regarding to hypothesis 4 which states "Female students show more academic achievement and emotional intelligence as compared to male students" was proved in present research. Results shown in table 4 revealed that female students are shown more emotional intelligence and academic achievement as compare to male students. Many earlier studies were explained that gender differences existed on emotional intelligence (Katyal & Awasthi, 2005; Mayer, 2001). Similar previous study results were supported our first part of hypothesis that Female students were more predisposed to have emotional intelligence as compared male students. It was observed that men are less emotionally expressive than women because they can understand and recognize emotions better (Mayer, 2001). Previous similar study was conducted to explore role of gender between grade point average and Emotional Intelligence. This study results were explained that those female students who experienced emotional intelligence, they shown better academic performance as compared to male who did not experience emotional intelligence (Katyal & Awasthi, 2005).

Similar prior studies were findings supported our second part of hypothesis that gender differences existed on academic achievement for last few decades (Eitle, 2005). Female students were more tend to have academic achievement as compared male students (Chambers & Schreiber, 2004). Similar, study have been elaborated that demographic variables such as gender, ethnicity, and father's occupation are notorious and crucial factors for student academic achievement (McCoy, 2005; Peng & Hall, 1995). Prior contrary study was explained that males students more likely to be academic achievement than female students (Abubakar, 2010; Eniayeju, 2010).

Regarding to objective 1 "To investigate the moderating role of emotional intelligence between academic procrastination, and academic achievement among male and female University students" was partially accepted in present research. Results shown in table 4 revealed that academic Procrastination was a significant predictor for Previous Class *GPA* among male and female students. Results of table also revealed that Emotional

intelligence was a significant predictor for Previous Class *GPA* ($B=-.147$, $p < .05$) in male students. On the other hand, Emotional intelligence was non-significant predictor for Previous Class *GPA* ($B=-.127$, n.s) in female students. The result indicated that interaction between academic Procrastination and Emotional intelligence was a significant predictor for Previous Class *GPA* ($B=-.25$, $p < .001$) in female students. Our study results revealed that emotional intelligence is moderator between academic procrastination and previous class *GPA* in female students. Several earlier research findings have been supported our study findings that Academic performance was predicted by academic Procrastination in educational settings (Jackson, Weiss, Lundquist, & Hooper, 2003; Schouwenburg, 1995; Tice and Baumeister, 1997; Akinsola, Tella, & Tella, 2007; Balkis & Duru, 2010; Fritzsche, Young, & Hickson, 2003; Özer et al., 2009). Previous similar study was conducted to explore role of gender between Emotional Intelligence and academic achievement. This study results were explained that those students who experienced emotional intelligence, they shown better academic performance as compared to those students who did not experience emotional intelligence (Sutarso, 1999).

Implications of research

For future research and for policy development the results of this study have important implications

- 1- Present study indicates the role of emotional intelligence between procrastination and academic achievement among university students. To understand in dealing with problems of university students it will be helpful for the teachers to interrelate with them according to their needs.
- 2- Focusing on emotional intelligence will helps in decreasing procrastination which will drag to good academic achievement.
- 3- One of the most effective factors in academic achievement id to develop sense of emotional intelligence which may also be a point of intervention.
- 4- Present study may also be helpful for teachers and students to understand the role of gender, age, socio economic class and educational level in students which is an important factor in procrastination.
- 5- Student counselling can be given to eradicate procrastination, moreover time-management techniques can also be taught to students.
- 6- Present study may help teachers and students in order to focus on emotional intelligence.
- 7- Parents and teachers both can help the student to work and focus on his emotional quotient.

Recommendations and limitations

Every research is a new step to understand the solution of the problem. Limitations in study encourage the researchers to fill the gaps in future research and to give way to new researches.

The present research has certain limitation like any other research in social sciences. One of the boundaries is the foundation of the inventories as a measure. Inventories are of course widely used instruments in social sciences but definitely with certain limitations. The element of social desirability affects the validity of the instrument. Inventory is developed keeping in view these hazards but still the element of social desirability cannot be completely eliminated. Only limited universities of Rawalpindi and Islamabad could be approached for the present study. Emotional intelligence is required more to be studied in Pakistani context. Very few researches were noted during the literature review by the researchers in Pakistan.

Beside all these limitations, the present study is pretty insightful in understanding the role of emotional intelligence and procrastination in the academic achievement of the students. Investigating the role of demographic factors in emotional intelligence also shares some valuable insights. Emotional intelligence is an area, which should be given much attention in Pakistan for the successful educational process. Emotionally intelligent students should be supported in education, and provide them privileges in their curriculum, to support and to take forward to lead Pakistan, prosperous.

A variety of programs, seminars and conferences should be organized in different cities of Pakistan which provide awareness to the teachers for improving the emotional stability of their students and educational management. Teachers in this regard, will be able to handle the students, their educational activities, educational management and it will help the students to perform better. It will also help the university administration in the enrollment of students.

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